

Influence of Sport Product Packaging on Consumer Decision Making Here the Case Study of Li-Ning Basketball Shoes in China

Jian Zhan Hong¹, Arti Pandey,² Supot Rattanapun*,³ Surasak Chaykhunthod,⁴ Phattaranit Wongboonyarit,⁵ Pataree Hansanontha,⁶ Arus Kongrungchok⁷

International College, Rajamangala University of Technology Krungthep, Thailand

Abstract: *This research was conducted in Guangzhou, attempting the deductive research method. Self-managed questionnaires were used to collect data on Chinese people. The collected data is numerical data. The purpose of the research is to study the factors of packaging that influences Chinese consumer's decision making. The target population of this research are current Chinese customers of Li-Ning basketball shoes who have experience with Li-Ning basketball shoes products. The customers will be selected in Guangzhou City of China and have the experience with Li-Ning's basketball shoes. The total number of customers is 400 Li-Ning's customers. The results show that product attributes, product design and product materials are significantly related to Chinese consumers' decision making for the Li-Ning's basketball product.*

Keywords: *Product design, product attributes, product design, customer's purchase decision making, Market competition, packaging design.*

I. INTRODUCTION

Nowadays, the green sportswear industry has become more competitive in the global market, it has pushed the sport businesses to their edge (Chen, Kan.&Chai, 2010). Especially, many different types of sportswear products are coming up to the market with many fashionable and recyclable packaging than the past edge. The packaging has two core functions. Firstly, it is to protect the product Secondly, it to promote product to consumers. The packaging of sportswear products in the past is to ensure the safety of transporting products. Now, the function of packaging is to ensure more healthy purpose and modern elements (Curry, 2011). The sportswear brands design the creative message in order to communicate meaning with customers in the decision-making process (Polyakova, 2013). Chinese customers mostly did not know what exactly they want to buy, some of them were price sensitive, they care about the price and quality. But now, more and more Chinese are caring about cultural elements on the packaging of product, (Park, 2019). It's possibly attracting Chinese customers by the design of the packaging. The packaging is like the communication tool, it is only to communicate with between Chinese consumer and the sport product at the point of purchase. (Kim, 2011) There are some choices that consumer will take decision before making a purchase. Initially, it starts once the consumer shows willingness to purchase a product (AlZubaidi, N. 2020). Then, the consumer decides which product to get. For example, what kind of brand, color or size to buy, how much time to spend when consumer makes the purchase. Finally, what kinds of method to use for making the payment. Yann and Klink (2017) pointed that the brand or business design the type of packaging to attract customers' attention in order to reach the point of purchase stage. The strategic goal of sportswear (Chow, J. C. 2020). brand or business is trying to display the product, design for the packaging, Add the detailed information through the label of the product. It is to explore the potential buyers. Designing of the effective sport product packages (Liu, 2013) is important to the brand or business' success in the modern society. It is also important to improve brand image while affecting consumer decision making. Thus, sport product packaging affects the Chinese consumer's decision making at Li-Ning basketball shoes (Zhu, N. 2017) . There are a few types of factors that affect consumer's decision making (Sahu, S. R. 2017)are packaging attributes (font style, color, the written information); the design of the packaging (modernization of design, illustration, uniqueness); Materials (Eco-friendly basis).

Therefore, the researchers agree that packaging would work as a communication tool for a specific product and build the special selling point of it, while it supports the concept of point of purchase.

Li-Ning considered as the pioneer of Chinese domestic sportswear brands in China, the brand name of LI-NING (Ning, L. (n.d.)) was the athlete's name. He registered this name as a sporting goods company in Beijing, China. Li-Ning was an Olympian gymnast (Hwang, Kang & Lee, 2018) who is an outstanding Chinese super hero, he won six gold medals at the 1984 Summer Olympics, which was the first game that he participated in. The world has given him with title "Prince of Gymnastics." (Russell, 2013). In 2008, he earned the chance to light the Olympic flame for the 2008 Beijing Olympics, he was wearing all the LI-NING logo's clothes from head to toe. (Mirroring the Olympic Games – The Beijing 2008 Olympic Games in the American media. 2013) Everybody knows him in China, he makes them so proud of him. He represented the whole sports spirit of China, like Michael Jordan in the sports field in the United States of America.

II. LITERATURE REVIEWS

A. 2.1 Definition

1) 2.1.1 Sport Product packaging

As the above chapter mentioned that the sport product packaging is like a tool to communicate with potential customers. way of communication representation. Design elements of the packaging should attract consumers' attention, so as to realize the direct marketing of the brand. The packaging pattern of sports products can also stimulate and persuade consumers more than the brand name, so as to make consumers purchase behavior. Product packaging actually not only protects products from transporting, but also can act as the presenter between brands and customers (Lee, W. 2014) .

Pointed that the sports product packaging role is to define the meaning of its product while creating the message about the brand into the market. (Define the product. 2019) Customers will note many different kinds of sports product packaging in the current sportswear market. According to (Patterns in packages: Learning from many packages and many attributes. In 2009, Chinese customers saw two types of sports product packaging, which are the first sports product packaging and the second sports product packaging . The first sports product packaging is to ensure the product safety under transporting. The second sports product packaging is to promote itself into the market for branding.

The brand identity on the Li-Ning basketball shoes sports product packaging is very important to communicate with Chinese customers and to create a positive image at the same time. The logo of the packaging has meaningful information, such as the traditional cultural dragon elements. It also can help to enhance the familiarity of the product to those customers (Zhang, X. 2015) . There are labeling, logo, and information about a product on the sports product packaging. It is also known as the container of the packaging. Additionally, it can also attract customers by creating attractive information on the label of the product packaging. Customers who buy a product will basically see the packaging first, so they will later decide whether or not to buy the related product mentioned.

B. 2.2 Packaging Attributes on Li-Ning Basketball Shoes Product

The attributes of the product come from different kinds of industry and the sports packaging attributes will be expressed according to the industry of the sport product and its own bright spots (Pitts, B. G. 1997) . Li-Ning basketball shoes require the designer to understand the product. The packaging attributes also need to better interpret the product itself and play a role in promoting the product (Dunn, T. 2015). Specifically, product attributes at Li-Ning basketball shoes, which are divided into two parts. The first part is verbal, which is talking about the basic information on the packaging. The second is the visual matter, which is talking about graphics, color, shape, size and packaging materials. Therefore, to do a good product packaging to attract customers, we must first establish the attributes of the product, understand the highlights of the product, and grasp the key points of the product to perform (Patterns in packages: Learning from many packages and many attributes. 2009).

1) 2.2.1 Font style

The font style is important for brands to create the positive image of the company and convince the customers with clear information about the product (Geovani, S.M, W., Ronald, D., & Amelia. 2021). The font style of the package produces positive energy to affect consumer's purchasing actions. Firstly, the inspirational font style, which could generate positive energy to potential customers and encourage them from being more active in social activities. It

positively directs them into the passionate lifestyle as much as to persuade them to buy a product in the end. The second is font size, the size decides what kind of possible sales achievements will occur. The effective font size is reliable and creative (Budi Cahyono, S. 2017). It combines with shadow and colors on the different sizes of it. The largest size style it's easy for customers to get aware of. It may lead to the point of purchase. Many great brands or businesses are having excellent practice for the font size. They know exactly when and how to make a reliable and creative font size for their customers.

2) *2.2.2 Color*

The color of the package produces a good feeling of connection with customers. Different colors have different feelings to the customers. For instance, pink, yellow and blue presents kind of warm emotions to customers. Instead, black, brown etc. Those dark colors represent a kind of feeling like ambition, aggressiveness and passion. Therefore, it is to build an impressive sense between product and customers (Feeling like a different kind of state. 2019).

3) *2.2.3 Written Information*

The written Information provides information in detail about the product. Somehow, it should be seen as easy as possible. Thus, the customers can easily reach the details of information about the product that they want. The written Information of the package plays a vital role in customer decision making. Customers will be concerned about buying a product if the information on the product is appropriate. Importantly, it enhances credibility between customers and product (Ekeha, 2010).

C. *2.3 Packaging Design on Li-Ning Basketball Shoes Product*

Packaging design includes form, shapes, front style, materials, color, with constant information. Li-Ning Basketball Shoes Product connects all those related methods in designing product, which is based on research development concept in order to match the market and the preferences of consumers (Du, 2019). It is to create a good image of the company, as it serves to identify and distinguish a sports product in the current marketplace. For the purpose, the excellent design of packaging is to gain the best reputation while generating a great sale of the company.

1) *2.3.1 Modernization*

The modernization of the package design is to support between the brand and customers. It makes more customers realize the product easier and perceive the good quality of a product (Geovani, S.M, W., Ronald., & Amelia. 2021). It creates the user-friendly concept that makes customers and brands more connected and capable as well as prevent damage. Moreover, the modernization of the product packaging must relate to the categories of the product. Sports product is always upgrading, so that the sport product packaging needs to follow the trend in order to design the suitable packaging to fit each different type of sports product.

2) *2.3.2 Uniqueness*

The uniqueness of the package design is to differentiate themselves from their competitors. In the past, packaging designs basically consisted of making the regular design, which is according to the company's strategy of packaging design. Customers might not differentiate clearly from other product packaging. because they all look similarly to others. In order to compete with competitors in the current market, many brands are willing to design special and unique product packaging. Sports brands like Li-Ning are to differentiate between many types of sports shoes products and create preferences among many different customers. To make sure their presences are matching with the design of packaging. Mostly in the Chinese market, the unique design of product packaging is related to the Chinese culture elements. For example, the dragon style, the moon style and the Tang Dynasty style will be covered in many brands' designs. Other than that, the unique design directly affects customers' buying behavior. It is impressive that the design can easily attract them from being aware of the product. Uniqueness of the design is the base of decision making, it directly drags customers' minds into the product. Therefore, have a creative and unique design of packaging is important for current business in order to achieve more sales (M., Samihardjo, R, &Nugraha, 2020)

D. *2.4 Packaging Materials on Li-Ning Basketball Shoes Product*

Packaging materials are usually made of plastic, fiber, or paper. However, Li-Ning is a green company that focuses on green concepts according to their product and the Chinese government's order. Since the Chinese government started developing the green concept, more and more brands are implementing this idea into their product design. Li-Ning is conducting the green concept and eco-friendly idea to their design of shoes product, which is more environmentally friendly. Making the decision on which type of packaging material to use is very important to the successful selling, transportation of product and sustainability issue.

Corrugated boxes have been a popular packaging material currently, which is recyclable, renewable, and environmentally friendly. Corrugated boxes have excellent structural stability for shipping, storing, and even marketing products. Corrugated boxes are also implemented and incorporated with Li-Ning right into your packaging. Hence, corrugated boxes are easily recyclable, completely renewable, and frequently reusable for those environmentally conscious companies like Li-Ning and their potential consumers.

1) *2.4.1 Eco-friendly Basis*

Corrugated cardboard is a packaging material made from one or multiple types of fiberboards and created through a fluted lamination process. Corrugated boxes performed into a traditional rectangular box shape and used for packaging and shipping products for many brands. It is recyclable materials, which can be used again and again after being possessed in a chemical treatment. Moreover, it is also renewable materials that are bio-based and can be naturally renewed (Sinha-Ray, 2020). Therefore, corrugated boxes are a popular packaging material, which is recyclable, renewable and eco-friendly.

E. *2.5 Customer Decision Making Theory*

There is a list of choices that are made by the consumer before making a purchase that initially starts once the consumer shows willingness to purchase a product. The consumer then decides which product to get, model, size and what brand to buy, followed by how much time to spend, when to make the purchase and finally what kinds of method to use for payment.

There are basically 5 stages of consumer decision making. Firstly, it is to recognize the problem that customers know what needs they want to satisfy or demand for a specific product. Then, it is to evaluate an alternative and to look for information, it means that customers start searching for the product information and want to know more about the specific item. Information must be searched for identifying all alternatives, so customers will share the information with their friends to know more about the product while gathering more data. The fourth stage is the purchase decision which is that customers consider buying the product. Lastly, post-purchase is that customers will be giving the feedback to the brand that they purchased, it is also important for brand or companies to measure the customer loyalty (Kall, J. 2021)

2.6 Research Hypothesis Development

This research is to explore the Li-Ning basketball shoes product packaging on consumers decision making in China. According to the previous studies, which suggests the researcher to obtain the possible outcome from the research. Research will set up the assumption and test the collected data after that, this is to decide whether the hypothesis is true or not, either reject or inject. Hence, the hypothesis is to support the ideas of the research. Hypothesis is basically predicting relationships between two or more variables, so researchers need to test it while finding the validity and reliability of the data (Pesaran, M. H. 2015). According to the development of hypotheses, one needs to discover the interrelationships of the research objective, research question, literature review, hypothesis, and theoretical framework. There is one dependent variable (Customer decision making at Li-Ning basketball shoes) and three independent variables (Sport product packaging attributes, sport product packaging design and sport product packaging materials). It is to identify the relationship between those variables. Also, it has to test the reliability.

1) *2.6.1 The relationship between product attributes and customer decision making at Li-Ning basketball shoes product.*

It requires the designer to understand the product. The packaging attributes also need to better interpret the product itself and play a role in promoting the product. Specifically, product attributes at Li-Ning basketball shoes, which are divided into two parts. The attributes of the product come from different kinds of industry and the sports packaging attributes will be expressed according to the industry of the sport product and its own bright spots (Pitts, B. G. 1997). Li-Ning basketball shoes require the designer to understand the product. The packaging attributes also need to better interpret the product itself and play a role in promoting the product (Dunn, T. 2015). Specifically, product attributes at Li-Ning basketball shoes, which are divided into two parts. The first part is verbal, which is talking about the basic information on the packaging. The second is the visual matter, which is talking about graphics, color, shape, size and packaging materials. Therefore, to do a good product packaging to attract customers, we must first establish the attributes of the product, understand the highlights of the product, and grasp the key points of the product to perform (Patterns in packages: Learning from many packages and many attributes. 2009). It positively directs them into the passionate lifestyle as much as to persuade them to buy a product in the end. The second is font size, the size decides

what kind of possible sales achievements will occur. The effective font size is reliable and creative (Budi Cahyono, S. 2017) . It combines with shadow and colors on the different sizes of it. The largest size style it's easy for customers to get aware of. It may lead to the point of purchase. Many great brands or businesses are having excellent practice for the font size. In addition, the color of the package produces a good feeling of connection with customers. Different colors have different feelings to the customers. For instance, pink, yellow and blue presents kind of warm emotions to customers.

H1: The sport product packaging attributes have a positive impact on Chinese consumer decision making at Li-Ning basketball shoes.

2) *2.6.2 The relationship between product design and customer decision making at Li-Ning basketball shoes product.*

Li-Ning Basketball Shoes Product connects all those related methods in designing product, which is based on research development concepts in order to match the market and the preferences of consumers. Li-Ning Basketball Shoes Product connects all those related methods in designing product, which is based on research development concept in order to match the market and the preferences of consumers (Du, 2019). It is to create a good image of the company, as it serves to identify and distinguish a sports product in the current marketplace. It is to create a good image of the company. In the past, packaging designs basically consisted of making the regular design, which is according to the company's strategy of packaging design. Customers might not differentiate clearly from other product packaging. the modernization of the product packaging must relate to the categories of the product. Sports products are always upgrading, so that the sport product packaging needs to follow the trend in order to design the suitable packaging to fit each different type of sports product. because they all look similarly to others. In order to compete with competitors in the current market, many brands are willing to design special and unique product packaging. Sports brands like Li-Ning is to differentiate between many types of sports shoes products and create preferences among many different customers. Customers might not differentiate clearly from other product packaging. because they all look similarly to others. In order to compete with competitors in the current market, many brands are willing to design special and unique product packaging. Sports brands like Li-Ning are to differentiate between many types of sports shoes products and create preferences among many different customers.

H2 - The sport product packaging design has a positive impact on Chinese consumer decision making at Li-Ning basketball shoes.

3) *2.6.3 The relationship between product materials and customer decision making at Li-Ning basketball shoes product.*

Since the Chinese government started developing the green concept, more and more brands are implementing this idea into their product design. Li-Ning is conducting the green concept and eco-friendly idea to their design of shoes product, which is more environmentally friendly. Additionally, renewable materials that are bio-based and can be naturally renewed (Sinha-Ray, 2020). Therefore, corrugated boxes are a popular packaging material, which is recyclable. For instance, corrugated boxes, which have been a popular packaging material currently, which is recyclable, renewable and environmentally friendly. Corrugated boxes have excellent structural stability for shipping, storing, and even marketing products, corrugated boxes are also implemented and incorporated with Li-Ning right into your packaging. Hence, corrugated boxes are easily recyclable, completely renewable, and frequently reusable for those environmentally conscious companies like Li-Ning and their potential consumers.

H3 - The sport product packaging material has a positive impact on Chinese consumer decision making at Li-Ning basketball shoes.

III. CONCEPTUAL FRAMEWORK

This research aims to examine the influence of sport product packaging in terms of product packaging attribute, product packaging design and product packaging materials on Chinese customers' decision making at Li-Ning basketball shoes. Hence, the study emphasizes finding the tool through which Chinese consumers trust the packaging material before reaching a point of purchase while presenting the attitude toward purchasing the product. the research design that directly explained where, when and how the researcher should collect and evaluate the findings for the research study. The survey will be conducted to show the responses from respondents, it is completely anonymous. The demographic information will also be provided.

Figure 3.1 The conceptual framework of the research

IV. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

F. 4.1 Population and Sample Selection

1) 4.1.1 Population

The target population of this research are current Chinese customers of Li-Ning basketball shoes who have experience with Li-Ning basketball shoes products. The customers will be selected in Guangzhou City of China and have the experience with Li-Ning's basketball shoes. The total number of customers is 400 Li-Ning's customers. The population is unknown.

2) 4.1.2 Sample

Probability sampling techniques will be conducted into this research in order to select a sample from the given population. The researcher will apply an equation proposed by Yamane (1967) at a confidential level of 95% with a precise level of 0.05. The customers will be selected in Guangzhou City of China and have the experience with Li-Ning's basketball shoes, both male and female. The total number of customers is 400 Li-Ning's customers.

There are four categories of probability sampling techniques, and as follows: simple random sampling, Systematic, Stratified sampling and Cluster sampling. Simple random sampling even individuals have an equal chance to be selected. Systematic sampling needs to find the sampling in the ratio by dividing the sample required for the population to create subsets of equal proportion and selecting the sample out from the subset based on the ratio. Stratified sampling divides the population into subsets according to the homogeneity among the unit within a specific subset and heterogeneity between different subsets. The last probability technique is cluster

V. DATA PRESENTATION

5.1 Reliability Test of Research Instrument

Coakes & Steel (2007) defined that reliability analysis evaluates the properties of measurement scales and the items that make them up. The procedure calculates a number of commonly used measures of scale reliability and also provides information about the relationship between individual items in the scale. Reliability analysis can determine the extent of the items in research questionnaires related to each other. Internal consistency reliability is aimed to have the homogeneity of items comprising a measurement scale. To verify the reliability of the research constructs, the internal consistency analysis (Cronbach's alpha) and item-to-total correlation are used to identify the internal consistency reliability of the proposed constructs. Cronbach's alpha is a model of internal consistency based on the average inter-

item correction. Cronbach’s alpha is suggested to be 0.742 for pilot study and 0.725 for the main. If a scale has a Cronbach’s alpha below 0.60, it could be considered for any roots of measurement errors. The item-to-total correlation value is suggested to be equal or greater than 0. The higher inter-item correlation explains that the items of a scale have a strong relationship to the latent construct.

Table 5-1: Reliability Result for Each Respondents from Survey

factor	Items	Cronbach’s alpha
Li-Ning Basketball Packaging Attributes	10	0.852
Li-Ning Basketball Packaging Material	8	0.859
Li-Ning Basketball Packaging Design	10	0.865

Notes : N=250

5.2 Data from Li-Ning Customers Demographic Characteristics.

The researcher uses descriptive statistics to analyze the demographic characteristics of 250 respondents.

Table 4-2: Percentage Presented by Gender from Respondents

Gender					
		Number of Respondents	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	male	159	63.6	63.6	64.5
	female	91	36.4	36.4	100.0
	Total	250	100.0	100.0	

Notes : N=250

According to Table 4-2 and data collected, 63.6% of the respondents are male and 36.4% of the respondents are female.

Table 5-3: Percentage Presented by Age from Respondents

Age					
		Frequency	Perce nt	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	18-23	78	31.2	27.5	20.2
	24-29	69	27.6	20.6	28.6
	29-35	61	24.4	22.9	51.2
	36 above	42	16.8	29	100.0
	Total	250	100.0	100.0	

Notes : N=250

According to Table 4-3,31.2% of the respondents are in the age group of 18 to 23 years old. Those between 24 to 29 years old attributed to 27.6% and the 29 to 35 years old group is 24.4 % and above 36 years old is 16.8 %.

Table 5-4: Importance of product packaging by Respondents

Do you think the product is important?					
		Frequenc y	Perce nt	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Yes	180	72	70.5	70.5
	No	70	28	29.5	100.0
	Total	250	100.0	100.0	

Notes : N=250

According to Table 4-4, 72% of the respondents’ responded as yes and 28% of the respondents responded as no.

Table 5-5: Data Presented by the Product Packaging Affect Customers' Purchase Decision Making

Do the product packaging affect your purchase decision making?					
		Freque y	nt Perce	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Yes	185	74	70.7	70.7
	No	65	26	29.3	100.0
	Total	250	100.0	100.0	

Notes : N=250

According to Table 4-5 data collected, 74% of the respondents' responded as yes, which means respondents choose a product solely based on its appearance whereas 26% of the respondents do not agree.

5.3 Date Presentation of Li-Ning Basketball Product Packaging Attributes (Font Style, Color and Written Information).

The descriptive data of Li-Ning basketball shoes packaging attributes (font style, color and written information) were presented in Table 0-5

Table 5-6 The Result of Frequencies Count for Font style, Color and Written

	N	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std. Deviation
Font Style	250	3	6	3.62	0.677
Color	250	3	6	3.81	0.705
written information	250	1	6	3.95	0.728

Notes : N=250

The Table 5-6, present the result for sub-topics of packaging attitude. Majority of the respondents agree that the font style correlates with their decision making. The agreement is observed as the mean value of 3.62 and standard deviation of 0.677. The research concluded from this mean value that font style does influence the consumer decision.

The color mean value standard at 3.81 and standard deviation 0.705. This result suggests that color does influence consumer decision making.

As per the data collected in this study, the written information is an important element to influence the consumer decision making. The mean value stands at 3.95 and standard deviation at 0.728, suggesting the written information does influence the consumer decision making.

5.4 Date Presentation of Li-Ning Basketball Shoes Product Packaging Design such as quality of material and eco-friendly material.

The basic descriptive data of packaging design which include modernization and uniqueness.

Table 5-7 The Result of Frequencies Count for Modernization and Uniqueness

	N	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std. Deviation
Modernization	250	3	6	3.85	0.602
Uniqueness	250	3	6	3.72	0.513

Notes : N=250

The Table 4-7, presents the result of packaging design. Majority of the respondents agree that the modernization and uniqueness of the design correlate with their decision making. The agreement is observed as the mean value uniqueness of designing is 3.72 and standard deviation of 0.513. The researcher concludes from this mean value that uniqueness of the design does influence the consumer decision.

The mean value of modernization of design is at 3.85 and standard deviation 0.602. This result suggests that modernization of design does influence consumer decision making and it is supported by the findings.

5.5 Date Presentation of Li-Ning Basketball Shoes Product Packaging Materials such as eco-friendly material related.

The basic descriptive data of packaging materials which are about eco-friendly materials.

Table 5-8: The Result of Frequencies Count for eco-friendly materials.

	N	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std. Deviation
Eco-friendly	250	2	5	3.91	0.895

Notes : N=250

The table 0-8, presents the result of package material. Majority of the respondents agree that the package material correlates with their decision making. The eco-friendly material means value standard at 3.91 and standard deviation 0.895. This result suggests that eco-friendly

5.6 Regression analysis.

The result of the regression analysis is shown in Table 0-9 and Table 0-10

Table 5-9 ANOVA Table

ANOVA						
Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
	Regression	1.702	5	.606	2.2	.108 ^b
	Residual	52.85	245	.377		
	Total	54.83	250			
a. Dependent Variable: Consumer decision making						
b. Predictors: Packaging Attributes, Design						

Note: All correlations are significant at 0.01 level; N=250.

*p< .05; **p< .01; ***p< .001

Table Coefficients table

Coefficients

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
	B	Std. Error	Beta		
(Constant)	5.15	.401		7.55	.000
Packaging Attributes	.112	.077	.108	1.806	.095
Packaging design	.016	.073	.009	1.678	.086

Note: N=250. *p< .05; **p< .01; ***p< .001

a. Dependent Variable: Consumer decision making

Regression analysis was conducted to test the hypothesis and outcome of it is reflected using three tables of Anova and Coefficient. The Anova table shows a sig. value of 0.095 for packaging attributes, 0.086 for packaging design, which is more than 0.005, hence the alternative hypothesis is rejected. Therefore, the result from the collected sample units, showed the correlation value of 0.112 between the packaging attributes towards the consumer decision making. The positive relationship between the packaging attributes and consumer decision making is supported. Therefore, the result from the collected sample units, showed the correlation value of 0.016 between the packaging designs towards the consumer decision making. There is a positive relationship between the packaging design and consumer decision making.

VI. CONCLUSION AND DISCUSSION

This study integrates descriptive analysis, reliability analysis and regression analysis to explain the influence of sport product packaging on consumer decision making. This research investigates the impact of subfactors, such as font style, color, written information, modernization of design, illustration, uniqueness of design, quality of material and eco-friendly material on factors and consumer decision making. In this chapter, the results derived from the data analysis are summarized in the first section. Following is the discussion of the results evaluating the contribution of this study. Next, the implication of this study is described as well. Followed by the section of limitation of this study and finally, recommendations and conclusion to conclude the research.

6.1 Conclusion

This chapter presents the survey according to the results from 250 Chinese Li-Ning Basketball shoes respondents. The SPSS software is conducted. It provides a detailed outlook of the information gathered by this study. The information enables the researcher to have an overview of the Li-Ning basketball shoes product packaging influence on Chinese consumer decision making.

The data presentation includes demographic data, data from each factor that influences consumer decision making. The factors such as packaging attributes which has sub factors such as font style, color and written information, the package design which has modernization of design and uniqueness of design and the package material which has eco-friendly material as subfactor. The result of the analysis of the data gathered by this study has provided a clear picture of Li-Ning basketball shoes product packaging and its positive influence on consumer decision making.

RQ1 is that sports product packaging attributes have a significant impact on the Chinese consumer decision making process at Li-Ning basketball shoes. The result from the collected sample units, showed the correlation value of 0.112 between the packaging attributes towards the consumer decision making. The positive relationship between the packaging attributes and consumer decision making is supported. Additionally, the packaging attributes also need to better interpret the product itself and play a role in promoting the product. Specifically, product attributes at Li-Ning basketball shoes. It positively directs them into the passionate lifestyle as much as to persuade them to buy a product in the end. Therefore, to do a good product packaging to attract customers, we must first establish the attributes of the product, understand the highlights of the product, and grasp the key points of the product to perform.

RQ2 is that sports product packaging design has a significant impact on the Chinese consumer decision making process at Li-Ning basketball shoes. The result of packaging design. Majority of the respondents agree that the modernization and uniqueness of the design correlate with their decision making. The agreement is observed as the mean value uniqueness of designing is 3.72 and standard deviation of 0.513. The researcher concludes from this mean value that uniqueness of the design does influence the consumer decision. In addition, It is to create a good image of the company, as it serves to identify and distinguish a sports product in the current marketplace. It is to create a good image of the company. In the past, packaging designs basically consisted of making the regular design, which is according to the company's strategy of packaging design. Customers might not differentiate clearly from other product packaging. the modernization of the product packaging must relate to the categories of the product. Sports products are always upgrading, so that the sport product packaging needs to follow the trend in order to design the suitable packaging to fit each different type of sports product. because they all look similarly to others.

RQ3 is that sports product packaging materials have a significant impact on the Chinese consumer decision making process at Li-Ning basketball shoes. The result of package material. Majority of the respondents agree that the package material correlate with their decision making. The eco-friendly material means value standard at 3.91 and standard deviation 0.895. This result suggests that eco-friendly. Furthermore, Therefore, corrugated boxes are a popular packaging material, which is recyclable. For instance, corrugated box, which have been a popular packaging material currently, which is recyclable, renewable and environmentally friendly. Corrugated boxes have excellent structural stability for shipping, storing, and even marketing products, corrugated boxes are also implementing and incorporating with Li-Ning right into your packaging. Hence, corrugated boxes are easily recyclable, completely renewable, and frequently reusable for those environmentally conscious companies like Li-Ning and their potential consumers.

The researcher uses mixed regression analysis on the data collected. The result presents that the purchase making decision is related to all the independent variables. The beta weight of all the factors proves that all of them had a positive significance that affects consumer decision making.

7. Limitations of this Study

This research study deals with current members of Li-Ning basketball shoes product. This study has few limitations. Firstly, this survey limits us to a pool of Internet users. Hence, the results may not be generalized to non-Internet users. Second, the samples of Internet users for this study were mostly those who are more knowledgeable about the Internet and are thus experienced Internet users. Therefore, the sample of respondents may be skewed toward more experienced Internet users. This may also restrict the generalizability of the findings. Due to the limitation of time a systematic random sampling was done. Also, the sample size is small to be called a true depiction of population as the study was limited to Li-Ning basketball shoes product members. Quantitative research method has been used to collect data which is better to analyze consumers' behavior from quantity so that the report will be more persuasive for future research.

Based on effective packaging and marketing of basketball shoes, managers must adhere to certain elements of packaging. According to the results from the research, managers must carefully consider certain key elements of packaging identified by the research which have significant influence on consumers' perception about the product. These elements are in two categories, which include visual and informational. The research reveals that visual elements that influence consumers' perception include font style, color, design, and material. This implies that during the design of a package for gloves, managers must carefully consider the size, color, graphics, shape, and material of the package. This shows that managers must give a higher consideration to the package design when designing the package for basketball shoes. Furthermore, color is the attractive visual element of Li-Ning basketball shoes packaging, therefore managers must consider the appropriate color when designing a package for basketball shoes.

REFERENCES

- [1] Denton, A. B. (2021). "Academic Libraries and Athletics Programs: The Current State of Select Marketing and Development Partnerships." *Southeastern Librarian* 69(2): 5-20.
- [2] Al Zubaidi, N. (2020). The relationship between collectivism and green product purchase intention: The role(Singh, Kumar et al. 2021) of attitude, subjective norms, and willingness to pay a premium. *Journal of Sustainable Marketing*,
- [3] Cheng, H., Fan, H., Hoshi, T., & Hu, D. (2019). Do innovation subsidies make Chinese firms more innovative? Evidence from the China employer employee
- [4] Chow, J. C. (2020). Heuristic Cascade of a strategic goal. *Strategic Policy Design*, 130-133. <https://doi.org/10.4324//9781003009009-12>
- [5] Curry, N. (2011). Walking the walk: how the theory of reasoned action explains adult and student intentions to go green. *Journal of Applied Business Research*, 27(3), 107-116.
- [6] Du, J., & Li, M. (2019). Research on market entry order and product development strategy of aerospace components based on game analysis. 2019 Chinese Control and Decision Conference (CCDC). <https://doi.org/10.1109//ccdc.2019.8832667>
- [7] Dunn, T. (2015). Saleable product versus product produced. *Flexible Packaging*, 149-154. <https://doi.org/10.1016//b978-0-323-26436-5.00018-7>
- [8] Ekeha, G. E. (2010). Product information search by online customers. *SSRN Electronic Journal*. <https://doi.org/10.2139//ssrn.1730162>
- [9] Entrepreneurship and market orientation: Mindset of Indigenous community. (2019). *Journal of Marketing and Consumer Research*. <https://doi.org/10.7176//jmcr//57-02>
- [10] Feeling like a different kind of state. (2019). *Feeling Like a State*, 153-175. <https://doi.org/10.1215//9781478005575-007>
- [11] Ge, L., & Li, C. (2020). Exploration on marketing strategy of foreign luxury brand in China. *International Journal of Information and Education Technology*, 10(5), 399-404. <https://doi.org/10.18178//ijiet.2020.10.5.1397>